

UKBOL LIBRARY PREPARATION (SPOTLIGHT PROTOCOL) SOP

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This workflow is based on the Santa Cruz Reaction (SCR) by Kapp *et al.* 2021 for library building of museum specimens, with modifications of Nguyen *et al.* 2023, termed “Spotlight”. The reaction volumes have been halved to reduce reagent costs, lower volumes have not been tested. Please cite the original publications if using this method:

SCR: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhered/esab012>; Spotlight: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhered/esad041>.

Note that this method also replaces the lowest tier in SCR (Kapp *et al.* 2021).

Prepare all buffers and reagents according to section B of the “UKBOL Accelerated Buffer and Reagent Prep SOP”.

Have the following prepared:

- i. **Amplitaq + SYBR green plate**
- ii. **EBT + SPRI**
- iii. **ET SSB Dilutions**
- iv. **P5/P7 adapter splint dilutions**
- v. **Reaction Mix**

Gather the following reagents before starting:

- Thaw and equilibrate the **Reaction Mix** and **ET SSB dilution** to room temperature before pipetting.
- Thaw **P5 and P7 splints** and place on ice.
- Set thermocyclers to run at 95°C and 37°C in advance ready for incubation steps.
- Collect 2 boxes of Rainin tips (for addition of reaction mix).

1. **Combine the input DNA and SSB**

- 1.1. Add 1.25 µL SSB (at 60.8ng/ul) to the 10 µL lysate plate using the iDOT (“ET SSB” protocol).
- 1.2. Vortex 30s, and spin down x2.

Spotlight	
DNA extract	10 µL
ET SSB [60.8 ng/µL]	1.25 µL
	11.25 µL

Note: if less than 10 µL extract, fill to 10 µL with EBT buffer.

2. **Denature the input DNA**

- 2.1. Heat DNA/SSB’s for 3 min at 95°C in a thermocycler with a 105°C heated lid.
- 2.2. Immediately cold shock in a cooling block or on ice for 2 min.
- 2.3. Spin down reactions for 5 seconds then place back on ice.

3. Add Adapters & Reaction Mix

- 3.1. Add splints using iDOT (“SCR Splints v2” protocol).
- 3.2. Add reaction mix to SSB/Splint/DNA plate using the Rainin. Release the handle to pipette slowly as reaction mix is viscous. Gently pipette mix when reaction mix is added.

Spotlight	
DNA + SSB	11.25 μ L
[2 μM] annealed P5 adapter/splint	1 μ L
[0.4 μM] annealed P7 adapter/splint	1 μ L
Reaction Mix	12 μ L
	25.25μL

- 3.3. Foil seal plates and pulse vortex for 10 seconds, spin down x2

It is crucial to mix well after adding reaction mix
PEG conc. is 19% in the adapter ligation reaction.

4. Incubate Reactions

- 4.1. Incubate reactions for 1 hour in a pre-heated thermocycler at 37°C, with the lid set to 50°C [Kapp *et al.* 2021, incubated for 45 minutes].

5. Clean Spotlight Reactions

HV 0.2mL 96 Well Extractor with Stand (aka “thin magnet”) Stamp from

<https://ariumlab.com/product-category/extractors/> .

Ensure EBT + SPRI and elution plates are at room temperature before starting.

- 5.1. Prepare two wash plates with fresh 80% ethanol (100 μ L) per well using the Integra Viaflow.

- 5.2. Prepare one elution plate with 10 - 15 μ L of EBT per well.

(NOTE: 10 μ L of eluate is required for the indexing reaction however at this volume it can be difficult to ensure the beads get fully resuspended, so excess EBT is added).

- 5.3. Spin down reactions for 5s then add the following to the reactions using a multichannel pipette:

Spotlight 1x bead clean	
Library	25.25 μ L
EBT buffer + 18% PEG SPRI (EBT + SPRI)	95 μ L
	120.25 μL

- 5.4. Seal the plate, vortex and incubate for 10 – 20 minutes at RT.

- 5.5. Add the tip comb to the magnet, add the magnet to the plate and let the beads concentrate until the solution is clear (~3 mins).

NB. Keep the remaining supernatant in case the bead clean fails (labelled “bind safety”).

- 5.6. Transfer the magnet with the beads into the first ethanol wash plate

- 5.6.1. Move the magnet up/down/side-to-side for about 30 seconds

- 5.6.2. Move the magnet into the second wash plate and repeat the above steps.

- 5.7. Remove the magnet from the ethanol washes and let the excess ethanol dry off (~ 30 sec).

NB. Ensure the beads do not over-dry.

- 5.8. Place the magnet into the EBT solution, quickly release the comb from the magnet & mix the beads with the EBT using the comb.
- 5.9. Incubate beads in EBT for 5 minutes at 60°C, then leave on the bench at RT for a further 5 mins.
- 5.10. Place the magnet back into the plate and let the beads concentrate (~1-2 minutes).
- 5.11. KEEP the ELUANT and store in the fridge until needed for further use.

The bind safety can be discarded after confirmation that the bead clean worked as anticipated

**** Safe Stop Point - can stop here and store reactions in fridge until ready for indexing PCR on the IconPCR****

6. Index PCR with the IconPCR

Indexing PCR is performed at half volume (but can also be performed at a quarter volume to reduce costs).

- 6.1. Retrieve a pre-prepared IconPCR plate that contains 12.5 µL of Amplitaq Gold 360 Master Mix and SYBR Green (final concentration 0.5x).
- 6.2. Add 2.5 µL of the combined indexes to the plate using the Integra Viaflow and take note of the indexes used in the space provided on the plate.
- 6.3. Add 10 µL of cleaned AL library using the Rainin.

Reagent	Volume (1 reaction)	Equipment	Room
Amplitaq Gold + SYBR Green	12.5 µL	Integra	Clean room
20 µM combined i5/i7 index	2.5 µL	Integra	
Library	10 µL	Liquidator	Pre-PCR room
	25 µL		

- 6.4. Seal with a qPCR seal, ensuring a tight seal with the qPCR seal applicator.
- 6.5. Vortex and spin down twice.
- 6.6. Run on the IconPCR machine with the following settings (“SCR Autonorm +1”):
 - Autonorm option:
 - Max 23 cycles
 - Min 5 cycles
 - RFU threshold 200
 - Additional Cycles +1

Ensure the run conditions are:

- 95°C for 10 minutes
- Library specific number of the following cycle conditions:
 - 95°C for 30 seconds
 - 60°C for 30 seconds
 - 72°C for **60 seconds**

- Final extension of 72°C for 7 minutes

6.7. The plates can be stored in the fridge until needed.

7. Pooling

- 7.1. Optional – Tapestation 1 column of each plate to ensure libraries look as normal and that the library prep was successful
- 7.2. Combine 5 μL of each well. Ensure only 1 μL of the negative control (H12) is added to the final pool. Final Pool Volume = 476 μL .
(Use a multichannel pipette to add 5 μL column by column from every well into an 8-strip tube, then combine from the 8-strip into a 2 mL tube)
- 7.3. Tapestation the uncleaned pools for each plate on a D1000 Tape.
- 7.4. Perform a **1.0X bead clean** on 200 μL of the pool and save the other half as a safety (Label: **UKXXX uncleaned**)
 - 7.4.1. Combine 200 μL uncleaned pool and 200 μL of room temperature AmPure XP beads, vortex and incubate for 15 minutes at RT.
 - 7.4.2. Do 2x 80% ethanol washes
 - 7.4.3. Elute in 100 μL of EBT for 5 – 10 mins.
Ensure you save the “bind safety”.
- 7.5. Tapestation the cleaned pool on a D1000 Tape. Depending on the amount of adapter dimer present another 1.0X clean may be done on the pool.
- 7.6. Add 20 -30 μL of the cleaned final pool into a new tube labelled with the batch number (**“UKXXX”**) to be handed over for sequencing.
Save remaining final pool (**“UKXXX cleaned FP”**) and store at -20°C for further sequencing if required.